

Anytime Reliability Analysis of Finite State Slow Fading Free Space Optical Channels

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Abstract—This letter presents a unified reliability analysis of the free space optical (FSO) channel. First, a finite state machine (FSM) framework is used to derive the Gallager error exponent under turbulence-induced fading. Then, a slow fading anytime coding scenario is analyzed, providing explicit upper and lower bounds for the achievable error exponent under streaming constraints. The error exponent is a channel characteristic which tells us how fast the probability of error goes to zero with increasing decoding duration. In the anytime setting, the error exponent tells us this rate for each bit depending upon its decoding duration. Thus an operator of the FSO communication system would know when he or she can stop accumulating received bits before decoding them finally so that a certain desired threshold of confidence in the decoded data may be met or surpassed.

Index Terms—Free space optical communications, finite state channel, Gallager exponent, anytime coding, slow fading.

I. INTRODUCTION

FSO links offer high data rates but are highly sensitive to turbulence-induced fading. Understanding the reliability function is crucial for robust coding. While Gallager's exponent quantifies block error decay, anytime coding addresses streaming reliability, bounding bitwise error probabilities under decoding delay constraints. This letter combines both aspects for an FSO link.

II. FSM-BASED RELIABILITY FUNCTION

Time variations in the refractive index are often suppressed in the treatment of optical wave propagation. – Section 3.2.3 of [1].

Turbulence is fundamentally a nonlinear process as described by the governing Navier-Stokes equations. Because of mathematical difficulties in solving these equations, Kolmogorov developed a statistical theory of turbulence that relies heavily on dimensional analysis and additional simplifications and approximations. Thus, turbulence theory as we know it today is not derived from first principles. – Section 3.2 of [1].

Consider the scalar FSO channel:

$$y_t = hx_t + w_t \quad (1)$$

where $\{w_t\}$ is Gaussian white thermal noise with zero mean, variance σ^2 and the noise is independent of the channel input $\{x_t\}$. h is the fading coefficient which follows the pdf,

$$f_H(h) = \frac{2(\alpha\beta)^{(\alpha+\beta)/2}}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} h^{(\alpha+\beta)/2-1} K_{\alpha-\beta}(2\sqrt{\alpha\beta}h) \quad (2)$$

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at any given instant, where the symbol Γ represents the gamma function and $K_{\alpha-\beta}$ the modified Bessel function of the second kind and order $(\alpha - \beta)$. The parameters α and β are directly related to atmospheric conditions and determine the turbulence strength. α and β are parameters describing the scintillation experienced by the plane waves, and in the case of zero-inner scale, they can be derived from the corresponding Rytov variance [3]. The input satisfies:

$$\sum_{t=1}^n x_t^2 \leq nP. \quad (3)$$

Motivated by the quotations at the head of this section, we undertake to model the FSO channel as a Finite State Machine [5]. Define the FSM state $s_t = (x_{t-1}, h_t)$. The Bhattacharyya distance is:

$$d_B((x_{t-1}^t, h_t^{t+1}); (\tilde{x}_{t-1}^t, \tilde{h}_t^{t+1})) = \quad (4)$$

$$-\ln \int \sqrt{p(y_t|x_{t-1}^t, h_t^{t+1}) \cdot p(y_t|\tilde{x}_{t-1}^t, \tilde{h}_t^{t+1})}. \quad (5)$$

Assuming the twiddle corresponds to a transmission of 1 and no-twiddle corresponds to a transmission of 0, we get that (using Equation (10) in [3]),

$$d_B((x_{t-1}^t, h_t^{t+1}); (\tilde{x}_{t-1}^t, \tilde{h}_t^{t+1})) = \frac{x_s^2(h_t^2 + \tilde{h}_t^2)}{4\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma^3} - \frac{\ln(\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma}. \quad (6)$$

Using this expression, in terms of it, we have the expression for the reliability function or error exponent from Merhav's paper,

$$E_0(\vec{q}) = - \sum_{s_t, \tilde{s}_t} q(s_t)q(\tilde{s}_t)d_B(s_t; \tilde{s}_t). \quad (7)$$

After plugging in the terms, and simplification we find,

$$E_0(\vec{q}) = - \frac{x_s^2}{4\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma^3} \left(\mathbb{E}_{s_t}[h_t^2] + \mathbb{E}_{\tilde{s}_t}[\tilde{h}_t^2] \right) + \frac{\ln(\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \quad (8)$$

where x_s represents the magnitude of the transmitted signal and σ is the standard deviation appearing in Equation (10) of [3].

III. CONNECTION TO ANYTIME RELIABILITY

The finite state machine derivation above provides a block coding error exponent for an FSO channel under turbulence. In many practical scenarios, data is streamed continuously, and bits must be decoded with minimal delay. The *anytime reliability* framework extends the block exponent to bound the

probability that a bit decoded after a delay W is incorrect. By combining the FSM-derived Gallager exponent with delay-aware sequential decoding, we can bound the error probability even when the channel experiences slow fading.

IV. SLOW FADING ANYTIME RELIABILITY

Block codes [2] and interactive communications are two forms of point-to-point communications where data integrity has to be maintained. Schulman [7] was one of the pioneers of the interactive setting. In the interaction paradigm two processors compute a function by sending bits to and fro. The computation is very sensitive to errors (as also synchronization between the transmitter and receiver) and so bits need to be repeated until each bit is received correctly. Block codes don't work in this setting since the processors typically do not know in advance what they want to transmit. Thus Schulman introduces tree codes which go beyond Wozencraft's random tree codes [8]. His protocol is efficiently implementable if there exists a tree code in which the label on any edge can be computed in time polynomial in the depth of the tree for a finite tree. For an infinite tree, this last factor gets replaced by the depth of the edge. By providing an efficient (polynomial time) implementation of the tree code "oracle," he proves a polynomial computation-time coding theorem for noisy channels.

A. Slow Fading Model

In typical atmospheric conditions, the FSO channel coherence time is much longer than the symbol duration but finite. We approximate this slow variation by dividing the total decoding delay W into N intervals, each with constant fading statistics. This piecewise constant model allows us to use the FSM-derived Gallager exponent within each coherence block, yielding tractable bounds for the overall anytime reliability.

V. ANYTIME ANALYSIS AND KEY RESULTS

A. Analysis

Consider a sequential semi-orthogonal repeated pulse position modulation (RPPM) tree code, built for the AWGN channel [6]. The error exponent for this channel is known under orthogonal signaling and maximum likelihood (ML) decoding. Denote it as $E_{orth_{w_1}}$ where w_1 is the variance of the white noise process. Note that whereas the remaining paper sections will use this exponent for simplicity of illustration (it is piecewise linear and quadratic) in the included figures, this term is to be replaced with the FSM-based exponent derived above.

In an anytime setting, the anytime exponent for this channel is found to be $W * E_{orth_{w_1}}$ where W is the delay at which decoding is performed. This assumes that throughout W symbol durations, the channel is constant. However, assume a slow fading scenario. Assume that the fading frequency is such that the fades or changes in the channel conditions occur at $0, \frac{W}{4}, \frac{W}{2}, 3\frac{W}{4}, W$ and so on, delays in units of symbol duration. So for a period of length $\frac{W}{4}$ symbols, the channel acts as an AWGN with some fixed variance w . During this

duration, we use an RPPM semi-orthogonal signal set designed for the variance w and ML decoding.

Next, the channel conditions change to v instead of w . During the next $\frac{W}{4}$ length period, we use an RPPM semi-orthogonal signal set designed for the variance v and ML decoding. Consider the overall probability of error.

- 1) Case 1: Pure AWGN channel (labeled "1") at delay W . This is the regular anytime exponent analysis. Therefore, $Poe_1 \leq \exp(-WTE_{orth_{w_1}})$ where T is the length of one symbol.
- 2) Case 2: AWGN channel "a" during delay from 0 to $\frac{W}{4}$ and AWGN channel "b" during delay from $\frac{W}{4}$ to $\frac{W}{2}$ and so on. During the 0 to $\frac{W}{4}$ delay, we have the bound $Poe_a \leq \exp(-\frac{WT}{4}E_{orth_w})$. During the $\frac{W}{4}$ to $\frac{W}{2}$ delay duration, we have the bound $Poe_b \leq \exp(-\frac{WT}{4}E_{orth_v})$. And similarly, we get Poe_c and Poe_d . An error at tree level x can get rectified at tree level $x + 1$ since all bits are repeated at each level. $Poe_a, Poe_b, Poe_c, Poe_d$ are the errors in the "new" bit introduced at each level upon channel condition *change*. An overall error in the decoding occurs if:
 - A. The path under channel a , of length $\frac{W}{4}$, produces an error which is never rectified¹, or,
 - B. The path under channel a , of length $\frac{W}{4}$, followed by channel b , of length $\frac{W}{4}$, produces an error which is never rectified, or,
 - C. The path under channels a through c , of total length $3\frac{W}{4}$, produces an error which is never rectified and so on.

Clearly, $Pr(A) = Poe_a$. The condition (B) occurs if either a w error occurs and is never rectified or a v error occurs and is never rectified or both occur and are never rectified. A w error in the first half of the segment under consideration will have one chance for rectification, namely in the following half. However, a v error will have no chance of rectification in the segment under consideration (the second segment). Thus $Pr(B) = Pr(a' \cup b)$, and $Pr(C) = Pr(a'' \cup b' \cup c)$ and so on.

Here, an a' type error is an a type error but with a single chance of rectification. Normally, if the channel had no fading,

$$Poe_{a'} \leq \exp \left\{ -\frac{WT}{4} \cdot E_{orth_w} - \frac{WT}{4} E_{orth_w} \right\} \quad (9)$$

and so

$$Poe_{a'} \leq \exp \left\{ -\frac{WT}{2} E_{orth_w} \right\} \quad (10)$$

But here we have fading and so,

$$Poe_{a'} \leq \exp \left\{ -\frac{WT}{4} (E_{orth_w} + E_{orth_v}) \right\}, \quad (11)$$

and so on².

¹The error won't be rectified, if we finalize the bit at the end of this much delay ($\frac{W}{4}$).

²A prime or apostrophe mark indicates the number of rectification chances ahead.

1) *Improving Channel Case:* Consider first the case of an improving channel. We have $Pr(OverallError) = Pr(A \cup B \cup C \cup \dots) \leq$ and so (by Union bound),

$$Poe_a + Poe_{a'} + Poe_b + Poe_{a''} + Poe_{b'} + Poe_c + \dots \quad (12)$$

$$\leq 4 * Poe_a + 3 * Poe_b + 2 * Poe_c + Poe_d \quad (13)$$

where we have assumed that the channel only improves with time. Thus,

$$Pr(OverallError_{improvingChannel}) \leq \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (N-i) * Poe_{i+1}. \quad (14)$$

where N is the number of parts the W delay has been broken up into (it was 4 in the preceding analysis above Equation (11)). Further, following Equation (11), we have in general,

$$Poe_{(i+1)(n)} \leq \exp \left\{ -(n+1) \frac{WT}{N} \sum_{j=i+1}^{i+1+n} \frac{E_{orth_j}}{n+1} \right\} \quad (15)$$

where the power (n) is the number of apostrophe marks and $n = N - 1$. This simplifies to,

$$Poe_{(i+1)(n)} \leq \exp \left\{ -\frac{WT}{N} \sum_{j=i+1}^{i+1+n} E_{orth_j} \right\} \quad (16)$$

For the specific improving case,

$$Pr(OverallError_{improvingChannel}) \leq \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_{j=0}^{N-1} (N-j) * \exp \left\{ -\frac{WT}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} E_{orth_{i+1}} \right\}. \quad (18)$$

Expressing $(N-j)$ as $\exp(\ln(N-j))$ in Equation (18) we can write,

$$Pr(OverallError_{improvingChannelAnySlowfade}) \leq \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{N(N+1)}{2} \prod_{i=0}^{N-1} \exp \left\{ -\frac{WT}{N} E_{orth_{i+1}} \right\}. \quad (20)$$

Call this Equation (20), the key result for an improving channel. Clearly the anytime exponent is then obtained by comparison with the no-fading case where we have

$$Pr(OverallError) \leq \exp(-WTE_{orth}) = \exp(-TE_{any}). \quad (21)$$

Thus,

$$E_{improvingChannelAnySlowfade} = \quad (22)$$

$$-\ln(Pr(OverallError_{improvingChannelAnySlowfade}))/T \quad (23)$$

which is plotted as solid curves in Figures 1, 2 and 3.

We obtain a lower bound to the exponent for the conditions under consideration. In essence we see that the lower bound to

Anytime Exponent vs Rate for $W \in \{1, 5, 20, 100, 200\}$, $N=1$

Fig. 1. Plot of anytime slow fading exponent lower bound with matching curves for the improving and degrading channel cases, $N=1$.

Anytime Exponent vs Rate for $W \in \{1, 5, 20, 100, 200\}$, $N=2$

Fig. 2. Plot of anytime slow fading exponent lower bound with an improving and degrading channel. Since $N=2$, the upper and lower bounds no longer match.

the anytime exponent of a slow fading improving channel depends on all the intervening channels' parameters. Thus, if the channels' variances change stochastically, the exponent bound depends on the slow fading "stochastic process." Also, for the improving channel case, we see that the greatest weight (4) in Equation (13) is for the earliest or first quarter- W segment and then the weights decrement. As a simplification, we could state that for the improving channel, a code which does much better earlier on, and degrades in or loses performance with increasing tree levels, might perform better in comparison with one which performs uniformly at every tree level. This insight could perhaps be exploited practically.

2) *Degrading Channel Case:* For a channel which is degrading we have, $Pr(OverallError) = Pr(A \cup B \cup C \cup \dots) \leq$ (by Union bound)

$$Poe_a + Poe_{a'} + Poe_b + Poe_{a''} + Poe_{b'} + Poe_c + \dots \leq \quad (24)$$

Anytime Exponent vs Rate for $W \in \{1, 5, 20, 100, 200\}$, $N=10$

Fig. 3. Plot of anytime slow fading exponent lower bound with an improving and degrading channel. $N=10$ is chosen to get smoother curves.

$$4 * Poe_a + 3 * Poe_b + 2 * Poe_c + Poe_d \leq 10 * Poe_d \quad (25)$$

where we have assumed that the channel only decays with time. This decay condition holds if $Poe_a < Poe_b < Poe_c < \dots$. Furthermore, $Poe_a > Poe_a'$ provided the possibility of rectification outweighs the degradation of the channel with time. Thus,

$$Pr(OverallError_{degradingChannel}) \leq \frac{N(N+1)}{2} \cdot Poe_N. \quad (26)$$

Next we note that

$$Poe_N \leq \exp \left\{ -\frac{WT}{N} E_{orth_N} \right\}. \quad (27)$$

Thus, analogous to Equation (20) we obtain,

$$Pr(OverallError_{degradingChannel}) \leq \quad (28)$$

$$\frac{N(N+1)}{2} \exp \left\{ -\frac{WT}{N} E_{orth_N} \right\}. \quad (29)$$

As a final note, since a general slow fading FSO channel will sometimes degrade and sometimes improve, its anytime slow fading error exponent lower bound should be sandwiched by the degrading case (worst case scenario) and the improving case (most optimistic scenario). Thus when actual fading conditions are not known, we can still provide a “regionalization” of the anytime exponent lower bound, i.e., that it lies within a region bounded by two exactly known curves. The dashed curves in Figures 1, 2 and 3 represent the degrading case. Figure 4 shows the derived bounds as a function of time, for different anytime delays W for rate $\frac{1}{2}$.

B. Key Results

To state the results succinctly, we find that a bound from above, on the anytime error exponent lower bound, which can

Fig. 4. Upper and lower bounds on the anytime exponent lower bound vs time for various W .

be expressed in terms of the probability of decoding error P_1 , can be obtained from,

$$P_1 \leq \frac{N(N+1)}{2} \prod_{i=0}^{N-1} \exp \left\{ -\frac{WT}{N} E_{orth_{i+1}} \right\} \quad (30)$$

where we have assumed that channel conditions improve gradually, W is the anytime delay, W/N is the coherence period of the channel, and $E_{orth_{i+1}}$ are the Gallager orthogonal signaling with maximum likelihood decoding error exponents for the consecutive distinct coherence periods introduced at the section head, for ease of illustration and to be replaced with the results of Section II.

In the degrading channel case, the bound we find is from below, on the lower bound, and is given by,

$$P_2 \leq \frac{N(N+1)}{2} \exp \left\{ -\frac{WT}{N} E_{orth_N} \right\}. \quad (31)$$

Thus, we “sandwich” the slow fading anytime lower bound from above and below, to our knowledge not done previously in the literature.

VI. CONCLUSION

A finite state machine model combined with anytime bounds provides insight into FSO link reliability under turbulence and streaming. Future work can explore practical coding designs and physical channel based simulations that exploit this structure³. To reiterate, our key contributions include: (a) An FSM based model to capture time variations; input-dependent state FSM to capture nonlinearities, and (b) a streaming analysis with piecewise constant FSMCs to capture modern data applications and the reliability involved in them.

³Note that since we have a finite state machine structure which is a channel with memory in general, unless the coding and decoding design doesn't exploit the memory structure, it may not be feasible to attain the theoretical bounds of this paper via physical layer simulations [4]. See also [9] though it is for the feedback case.

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